

Thin-Compartmented Reservoir Simulation and Quantitative Interpretation Using Seismic Attributes: A Case Study in 'Jude Field', Offshore Niger Delta

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Article History:

Received: 03.05.2025 Revised: 17.05.2025 Accepted: 05.06.2025 Published: 13.06.2025

ABSTRACT:

Thinly bedded hydrocarbon reservoirs are often by-passed during most exploration activities. Unfortunately, fewer research activities have been done within these unobvious by-passed zones. In recent times as technology advances, reservoir characterization within thin beds has improved. Notable high resolution and optimal strategies were established in Agbada formation, Niger Delta for exploring thin compartmentalized reservoirs, predict the viability and reservoir effects, and generate relevant models conditioned by seismic. This was achieved using the results obtained from well logs and seismic data through a complete evaluation involving integrating geological, petrophysical, and seismic interpretation combined with advanced rock physics modelling of thin bedded reservoirs in the study area. Reservoir architecture, thicknesses, seismic properties which control the reservoir quality, and the rock properties that control the seismic signal were also determined. Three reservoirs (AJ2, BJ2 and CJ2) were identified and correlated across the wells using gamma ray, resistivity and neutron-density logs. The results of the petrophysical analysis showed that there are variations in the evaluated parameters within the correlated reservoirs. The porosity value ranged from 25% - 35%, hydrocarbon saturation ranged from 0.49-0.79 and the volume of shale varied from 0.04 to 0.22. The outcome of the rock physics models affirmed the proven relationship existing within the elastic and reservoir properties. This further confirmed that by-passed zones (thin reservoirs, pinch-out, off-laps, etc.) could contain reasonable amounts of unexplored hydrocarbons. A new model, Power Law equation was generated from the cross plot of velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) against acoustic impedance (AI) which was used in obtaining reservoir data inter-wells especially where there are no wells in the study area. This is in contrast to the linear equation earlier generated for conventional (thick) reservoirs. The modelled properties revealed good storage capabilities, favourable description of reservoir distribution and significant interconnectivity.

Keywords: Cementation, Diagenesis; Depositional Trend; Elastic parameters; Quantitative Interpretation.

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INTRODUCTION

[6] discovered that only 40% of the geological formations within the sedimentary basins of our planet containing hydrocarbon have been explored. Generally, above 30% of these in situ reserves are constricted within thinly-bedded units [25]. Nearly all the thin beds are by-passed zones. There are numerous uncertainties about thin beds because of their complex structures and the collective log response it gives within specified log interval. Hence, it is paramount to find the true potential to reduce drilling risk with minimal uncertainty. There are few research activities based on the unapparent and often by-passed zones. Several researchers worked on the hydrocarbon prospectivity of Niger Delta with concentration on structures of obvious dimensional ratio. However, there is little or no exploration going on in the Niger Delta presently, rather, the development of existing fields. Therefore, there is a need for detailed study of these unobvious by-passed zones. These unapparent zones are associated with complicated structures like thin beds, pinch-out, off-laps etc. Entrapped within such structures is a reasonable amount of hydrocarbons that are yet to be explored. The expanse of oil (known and undiscovered) is limited hence, there is need to find new or more cache that will substitute for those that have been expended and meet the rising global energy demand. A thin bed (actually a sand body) is represented by a seismic event that falls below the level of seismic resolution and it occurs in all geologic settings. Thin beds are also beds whose resolutions are lower than the resolution of the logging devices used to characterize them [25]. Hence, thin bed analysis is crucial. When misinterpreted or by-passed, it could lead to significant under-estimation of hydrocarbon within the reservoir units, bringing about colossal investment profit loss [25]. According to [26], the range of limit of a thin bed could be defined based on the complexity of the structures in the field of study. This might be as a result of intense faulting giving rise to compartmentalisation, possibly depositional extension of reservoir units especially in underdeveloped fields where well control is sparse and sand depositional environments are laterally heterogenic with characteristic of fluvial-type settings. [7] studied the tuning behaviour of the-general case of arbitrary pairs of reflection coefficients. An achievable and broadly established definition of minimum resolving span that correlates with the Rayleigh's standard of Crest and trough partition at $\lambda/4$ [8] which is at tuning point where the compound amplitude is maximum. [9] used Seismic Inversion & Continuous Wavelet Technique (CWT) in generating instantaneous and multi-dimensional attributes for structural mapping and stratigraphic interpretation in Cambay Basin, India. However, low frequency events that are closely spaced in time domain were not resolved adequately. [10] applied special decomposition techniques (DFT and Hilbert transform (HT) where complex attributes were enhanced. This helped in visualization of small-scale structures and reliable estimates of wavelet and stratigraphic parameters was done. From the methodology, longer windows could only average the response to get better statistical representation but subtle microstructures and fine details were overlooked. [2] generated models from rock physics for accurate fluid differentiation of reservoir fluid.[5] utilized the models to affirm the results from seismic and define the relationship between the fluid and the rock properties. [17] used 3D seismic data with magnified resolution to image the thin gas sands of Khadro facies in various fields in the lower Indus basin, Pakistan. Most favourable deep learning method was developed and used for characterizing the thin beds from which maximum frequency acoustic impedance synthetics were generated using a deep neural network (DNN) and continuous wavelet transform (CWT) at reservoir levels. The results were validated with functioning geological facies. The extended seismic volume with increased frequency limit validated the presiding frequency and deciphered the thin beds.

All the afore-mentioned researchers used different techniques singly with a view to characterising thin reservoirs. However, a full integration of petrophysics, spectra decomposition, rock physics in reservoir characterization study of thin reservoirs is still missing within the static and dynamic reservoir models. All these have been done for structural interpretation within obvious and simple

structures. However, the comprehensive integration of petrophysics, seismic interpretation, and advanced rock physics analysis in the reservoir characterization study of thin reservoirs is still missing. Such a study is uncommon within the clastic thin reservoirs of the Niger Delta.

The field of study consists of series of thin and compartmented channel fill deposits which are difficult to resolve on seismic data. Vertical resolution of a 3-D seismic data set within the reservoirs of interest in Agbada formation, Niger delta was increased. This was achieved by spectral enhancement which showed a peak frequency of about 25HZ at AJ2 and BJ2 horizons and also improved the seismic to well correlation. The understanding of the relationship between the rock and fluids properties as well as the geology of the selected reservoirs (thin-bedded or conventional) is very relevant to revealing deductions that could assist the maximum extraction of oil and gas volumes from the hydrocarbon field. This is also crucial in estimating the hydrocarbon-in-place and the amount that can be recovered within the reservoirs. To avoid the common pitfall of mapping without limitation of the geological match that is represented by the event or amplitude, it is important to merge available data to predict accurately the response (seismic) for different types of fluid and lithology. Rock physics provides a way of relating elastic properties such as the bulk modulus, acoustic impedance, etc. to measured physical properties within reservoirs [12,21] These relations helped to provide a more accurate means of measuring and predicting the variation of these physical properties within the reservoirs. Therefore, this work presents a study using an integrated technique through effective characterization of the reservoirs in which the viability and reservoir effects of thinly bedded units were predicted, and also appropriate models were generated. It presents an innovative contribution to the field of thin reservoir analysis and hydrocarbon exploration.

GEOLOGY OF THE AREA OF STUDY

Mapping thin beds has maximized exploration potentials across the globe in which Niger Delta basin is not exempted. The Niger delta basin also called the Niger Delta territory, is an inferential basin with diverse faults and compound structures [11,32]. The Niger delta basin is one of the enormous basins in Africa. The study area ('Jude Field') falls within the south-western margin of the off-shore depobelt of Niger Delta. It is located between Latitudes 4.2° N - 4.5° N and Longitudes 5.0° E - 5.3° E covering an area of 180 square km (44,180 acres). Figure 1 illustrates a schematic sectional map of the Depobelts in Niger Delta and the study area. From the Eocene to date, the Delta has moved progressively southward, giving rise to depobelts that constitute the major dynamic portion of the Delta at every phase of its evolution [28]. Niger Delta province comprises of only one associated, high-yielding petroleum system [12]. The primary source rock is the lower Akata formation, the marine-shale facies of the Delta.

Figure 1. Niger Delta Map Showing the Basemap of the Study Area with Location of the Wells and the Petroleum Systems
Source: Modified by [21,22]

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The available dataset used in this study include a full suite of wireline logs that consist of the conventional logs and processed data set of 3D seismic in SEGY format. Four wells were used out of the five available because the depth of penetration in well 02 was small compared to the other wells.

Interpretation was carried out using software such as PETREL™ and Rokdoc.

Petrophysics

A suite of well logs and 3-D seismic data were integrated for both qualitative and quantitative interpretation. Performing petrophysical evaluation along with geophysical analysis has lots of advantages, thus it links the reservoir properties input to the rock physics modelling process. From well logs, qualitative evaluation (quick look method) is carried out [4]. Different lithologies were delineated (reservoir from non-reservoir) using the gamma-ray log. There are high radioactive elements in shale formation which are shown from the deflection of the log to the right of the baseline while the sand formations are deflected towards the left because of little radioactive elements. Hydrocarbon bearing zones were detected in the thin reservoirs using the resistivity logs with high resistivity values while water-bearing zones have low resistivity values. Oil and gas were differentiated using the porosity logs. Elastic properties generated were used in determining the relationships from which information about the reservoir rocks are deduced. The petrophysical parameters are also calculated from relevant equations.

Porosity Determination

Total porosity and effective porosity were calculated. Porosity was calculated using neutron and density logs.

Equation 1 is used from Petrel to calculate total porosity:

$$\phi_T = \frac{\phi_N + \phi_D}{2} \quad (1)$$

Where ϕ_T = total porosity, ϕ_N Neutron porosity; ϕ_D = Density porosity, which is calculated from equation 2

$$\phi_D = \frac{\rho_{ma} - \rho_b}{\rho_{ma} - \rho_f} \quad (2)$$

ρ_{ma} is density log reading in 100% matrix of the formation, default is 2.65; ρ_f is the density of formation fluid in the vicinity of borehole (mud filtrate); ρ_b is the density log reading in the zone of interest.

Effective porosity (ϕ_{eff}) is calculated by combining corrected neutron and density porosities using the formula,

$$\phi_{eff} = \sqrt{\frac{\phi_{Nsh}^2 + \phi_{Dsh}^2}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where ϕ_{eff} = effective porosity, ϕ_{Nsh} = Neutron-porosity reading in a shale zone, ϕ_{Dsh} = Density-porosity reading in a shale zone,

Petrophysical Evaluation

Well correlation within the four available wells: Jude 001, Jude 003, Jude 004, and Jude 005 was carried out to know the lateral distribution of the sand from one well to the other, developed at

corresponding duration within the field. This was done along the strike direction. The sand packages have thin beds towards the NE - SW direction as observed from the correlation panel (Figure 2). The result from the petrophysical evaluation is presented as Tables. Three thinly bedded reservoirs were tied transversely within the wells using both the gamma-ray log, resistivity log, and the porosity logs. The delineated reservoirs are Reservoirs AJ2, BJ2, and CJ2, though other reservoirs are present at deeper depth. Details on AJ2 and BJ2 are given here. A comparative correlation of the logs showed that the gamma-ray adequately separated shale from the sand. The fluid type in the reservoirs was delineated using the porosity logs (neutron and density). The clean sand and shale baselines were defined through a correlation between qualitative observation and quantitative evaluation of gamma-ray which is proportional to the clay content.

Figure 2. Log Response of Jude 001 Showing Gamma Ray Log, Deep Resistivity Log, Neutron Log, Density Log, Sonic and Volume of Shale Log

Rock Physics

The relationships in Rock physics are significant elements in the analysis and modelling of petrophysical parameters and seismic attributes for hydrocarbon exploration [1]. Rock physics is useful in reservoir evaluation to quantify lithology, porosity, and saturation, define net sand and net pay cut-offs. Rock physics rely on models based on a variety of measurements which give details of the density and elastic properties of both rocks and fluids. From the Rock Physics models, templates are obtained in the form of charts and graphs. One of the major factors in minimizing the risk relating to hydrocarbon exploration is precise representation of a reservoir in connection with lithology and fluid content. Besides, it helps in enhancing pore pressure prediction accuracy to mitigate drilling risks. This tool is very important in verifying hydrocarbon anomalies, most especially in un-drilled areas thereby reducing the exploration risk [23]. It involves precise speculation of the predicted acoustic properties for reservoir rocks and pore fluids under flexible conditions. Different phases carried out in rock physics analysis are:

- i). Cementation analysis
- ii). Lithology delineation
- iii). Fluid differentiation
- iv). Fluid substitution

Derived elastic and reservoir criterion overlaid on some fixed rock physics models were cross-plotted. The resultant clusters were used to identify or detect anomalies which could be interpreted as the presence of hydrocarbon or other fluids and lithologies [5]. The model used is the Contact Model, such as friable sand and cement models which were superimposed to know the rate of cementation or stiffness of the sand. Gaussian stimulation was done for fluid substitution, providing an accurate description of the reservoirs and the spreading of the reservoir properties within the geological units. The use of this plot will be explained below. The outcome of the Rock Physics Template (RPT) study is subject to the information obtained from the regional geology and utilizing the appropriate model. The elastic parameters were calculated using relevant expressions.

Rock Physics Analysis

For this study, elastic properties of the thin reservoirs AJ2, BJ2, and CJ2 at various depths were cross-plotted against parameters obtained from well logs (Figure 3). This was useful in visualizing the behavior of the reservoir properties and the elastic parameters which revealed detailed information about the degree of cementation within the reservoir, lithology, fluid distribution etc. Specified physical relationships (rock physics templates) were derived for the thin beds connecting the geophysical measurements to the attributes of interest. Different forms of RPT were generated between compressional velocity (V_p) and porosity (por) for cementation analysis; velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) and acoustic impedance (AI) for lithology delineation and fluid distribution; lambda-rho ($\lambda\rho$) and mu-rho ($\mu\rho$) for fluid distribution i.e. differentiating between oil sand, brine, and shale; bulk modulus (K) and porosity (Por) for fluid substitution.

Figure 3. Working Intervals of Reservoirs AJ2 and BJ2 in Jude 001 Showing the Well Logs and the Generated Elastic Logs

Cementation Analysis

The cross-plot of compressional wave (P-wave) velocity versus porosity, with depth (MD) as the third axis is useful in knowing the rate of cementation within an environment. Contact model, including the friable sand and cement contact was used to quantify the stiffness or softness of the rock within the reservoirs of interest).

Lithology Delineation

Lithology composition was delineated from the scatter-plot of compressional wave velocity (V_p) against acoustic impedance (AI). It is typical of the interpolation of sand and shale present in Agbada formation, Niger Delta. With density values as background colour, it clearly showed that the lower values define the reservoir zone and the reservoir boundary.

Fluid Identification

The velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) cross- plotted against acoustic impedance (AI), colored with a gamma-ray log is useful in identifying the fluids within the wells. V_p is affected by gas in the pore spaces and tends to travel at a slower velocity while the V_s is unaffected. Thus, the velocity ratio reduces. Smaller values of V_p/V_s and moderate acoustic impedance constitutes oil sand and a higher value of V_p/V_s indicates wet shale.

Fluid Distribution

This is the cross- plot of mu-rho ($\mu\rho$) against lambda-rho ($\lambda\rho$) with density log as the third axis showing the distribution of different fluids within the reservoirs of interest. It is otherwise called Rock Physics probability - density function. The lithology is divided into four litho-types which are shale, brine sand, oil sand, and gas sand.

Fluid Substitution

Fluid substitution is a major part of quantitative analysis used in modelling and evaluating the diverse fluid scenarios. A major challenge faced in quantitative interpretation using rock physics is predicting the parameters of the rock in the company of different fluids. The conduct of the dry rock is understood when the Gassmann's fluid substitution is performed. The switch from one fluid to a different one is modelled. It is essential to remove the effects of the initial fluid before modelling the current fluid. Prediction of the velocities of the filled rock can be achieved from the dry rock velocities and vice-versa. In general, the preliminary pore fluid is emptied from the saturated rock, thereafter, the moduli and bulk density are evaluated. The properties of the porous frame is adequately determined, then the rock is saturated with the pore fluid. The preliminary effective bulk modulus and density are analyzed. This is superimposed on the existing generalized template to deduce the common behaviour of the field. There is a significant increase in the pore fluid pressure and change in the volume from seismic waves that affect the rock and stiffens it. Based on Gassmann's equations, the shear modulus for isotropic medium is not dependent on pore fluid. Therefore, no change is observed during the fluid substitution process. However, the assumption could be violated (in case of breaking or crack-like pores).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three hydrocarbon bearing thin sands were delineated from the petrophysical analysis. For the thin pay sand less than 15m in Jude field, reservoir characterisation was reasonable. The result is shown in Table 1 while the histogram of the distribution of the petrophysical parameters is shown in Figure 4.

Table 1. Petrophysical Parameters of Jude 001, 003 and 004

Well	GT (m)	NT/G	Φ_T	S_w (%)	S_h (%)	V_{sh}	Φ_e	BVW (%)	K (md)	HCPV
Jude 001	13	0.9	0.30	21	79	0.10	0.27	6.3	1012	23.7

Jude 00 3	10	0.78	0.25	51	49	0.22	0.20	13	2354	12.25
Jude 00 4	11.5	0.9	0.33	21	79	0.10	0.30	6.9	2169	26.1

Note: where V_{sh} – Volume of shale, S_w – Water saturation, NT/G – Net to Gross, S_h – hydrocarbon saturation, Φ_e – Effective porosity, BVW – Bulk Volume of Water, GT – Gross Thickness, K – Permeability, HCPV – Hydrocarbon pore volume.

Figure 4. Histogram of the Distribution of the Petrophysical Parameters in Reservoir AJ2 Across the Wells

Note: Where Φ – porosity, S_w – Water saturation, S_h – hydrocarbon saturation, V_{sh} – Volume of shale, Φ_e – Effective porosity, BVW – Bulk Volume of Water, K – Permeability, GT – Gross Thickness, HCPV – Hydrocarbon pore volume.

Rock Physics Result

Cementation Analysis

The clusters in blue colour represent sand while the red clusters represent shale at a deeper depth (Figure 5 a & b). The blue clusters fall below the friable sand model as the colour code changes with depth. The red clusters fall between the constant cement- contact cement models and beyond. From the figure, the sand is loose, friable, and unconsolidated. It showed that shale consolidates with the presence of little cement to a certain level. The normal depositional trend for the sand within the marine environment is evident unlike the depositional trend of the sand on the continental shelf. It further revealed the diagenetic trend as the rock becomes stiffer and compacts with the depth of burial.

Figure 5a. Cross-Plot of Vp against Porosity Colored with Depth in Reservoirs AJ2 for Cementation Analysis

Figure 5b. Cross-Plot of Vp against Porosity Colored with Depth in Reservoirs BJ2 for Cementation Analysis

Lithology Identification

A contrast between sand (low gamma-ray values) and shale (high gamma-ray values) because of the presence of radioactive elements was established. The target (sand) was distinguished from the non-target (shale) (Figure 6 (a), (b) & (C)). From the rock physics template, the geology of the environment is seen to be responsive to the elastic parameters. From the data distribution, P-imp could not distinguish sand and shale lithology. There are too many overlapping data in P-imp ranging from 3500 – 7000 g/cc*ft/s and from 2600 – 9000 g/cc*ft/s respectively in Figure 6(c) where low V_{shale} (sand indicating) and high V_{shale} (shale indicating) converge. P-imp may give bad result for differentiating boundaries of the reservoir.

Figure 6 (a). Cross-Plot of Compressional Wave Velocity (Vp) against Acoustic Impedance (AI) Colored with Bulk Density for Lithology Delineation for AJ2

Figure 6 (b). Crossplot of Compressional Wave velocity (Vp) against Acoustic Impedance (AI) colored with bulk density for lithology delineation for BJ2

Figure 6 (c): Crossplot of Porosity against P-impedance

Fluid Identification

The sand is indicative of the pay-zone. Predominantly, shale has a higher value of the V_p/V_s ratio than sandstone. Shear wave does not disseminate through fluids.

Lower acoustic impedance is exhibited by sand package accommodating hydrocarbon while shale has higher acoustic impedance because velocity increases with depth.

It showed that the seismic velocity of a porous media is dependent upon the fluid within the pores. Oil saturated sand has lower gamma-ray values than that of shale because of the absence of radioactive elements in the sand. These radioactive elements are present in shale except in radioactive sand. Red and yellow coloured clusters have higher gamma-ray values representing shale while the clusters colored in blue and green represent oil-saturated sand (Figure 7 (a (& b))).

Figure 7 (a). Rock/Fluid Classes of Acoustic Impedance (AI) versus Velocity Ratio (Vp/Vs) colored with Gamma-ray for Fluid Identification across Reservoir AJ2

Figure 7(b). Rock/Fluid Classes of Acoustic Impedance (AI) versus Velocity Ratio (Vp/Vs) colored with Gamma-ray for Fluid Identification across Reservoir AJ2

Based on the well elastic and petrophysical data, a multivariate linear regression was derived for fluid saturation. Within the study area, the following rock/fluid classes were discriminated by reference to seismically derived attributes:

- i. Clean gas sands = low P-wave impedance, low Vp/Vs ratio (~5 000, <2.2)
- ii. Brine sands = high P-wave impedance, intermediate Vp/Vs ratio (~7 000, >2.25)
- iii. Laminated gas sands = reduced P-wave impedance and Vp/Vs ratio (~5 000, ~2.7)
- iv. Shales = higher P-wave impedance, high Vp/Vs ratio (>5 500, >2.5)

Fluid Distribution

There is a noticeable trend of overlapping oil sand - gas sand which relates to the fact that as the rock stiffens with depth and cementation increases, the fluid sensitivity decreases (Figure 8(a)). Low lambda-rho ($\lambda\rho$) and mu-rho ($\mu\rho$) values with lower density are interpreted as sand containing hydrocarbon (gas and oil) while the reddish clusters with high Lambda-rho ($\lambda\rho$) and mu-rho ($\mu\rho$)

values with higher density values are wet shale (Figure 8 (b)).

Figure 8 (a). Scatter Plot of Mu-rho ($\mu\rho$) against Lambda-rho ($\lambda\rho$) in Reservoir AJ2 for Fluid Distribution

Figure 8 (b). Scatter Plot of Mu-rho ($\mu\rho$) against Lambda-rho ($\lambda\rho$) in BJ2 for Fluid Distribution

Fluid substitution: The effect of stiffness on fluid substitution is analysed by cross-plotting porosity against normalized bulk modulus (K_{sat}/K_o). The noticeable change of compressional velocity in the stiffer cemented sand is less than observed in the softer uncemented sand (Figure 9). The elastic properties of the fluid are considered as an average under different conditions; when the fluids are partially saturated, uniformly saturated, or fully saturated with hydrocarbon or with water. The wide spacing of the lines indicates relatively soft rock, whereas closely spaced lines indicate stiff rocks. Rock properties such as sand thickness, fluid distribution, cementation analysis, porosity, etc. were also determined. Elastic parameters (e.g. Compressional and shear wave modulus, Young Modulus, lambda-rho, etc.) were estimated from the knowledge of lithology, porosity, permeability, and saturation of the fluid at reservoir condition.

Power Law Equation

Different equations can be used in the estimation of velocity ratio or acoustic impedance. The equation can be polynomials, straight line, exponential, power-law, etc. The best fit option of equation considering the lithology and fluid distribution within thin reservoirs is the Power Law, in contrast to the linear equation generated for conventional (thick) reservoirs by Abe et al. (2018). This might be

due to a significant difference in layer thickness. The new model, Power Law equation was generated from the cross-plot of velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) versus acoustic impedance (Figure 10).

This equation is effective and also important in estimating velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) using acoustic impedance or conversely. The equation is:

$$\text{Velocity ratio } (V_p/V_s) = 5549.066 * AI^{0.893} \text{ i.e. } Y = a * X^b$$

Y = velocity ratio (V_p/V_s); a = ~ 5549. 07, a constant; X is acoustic impedance (AI); b is ~ 0.893, a constant.

Figure 9. The Output Result for Fluid Substitution and Stiffness in Sandstone

Figure 10. Power Law Equation of Velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) against Acoustic Impedance (AI). The Red Clusters Represent Shale, Yellow Clusters Represent Brine Sand while Clusters Colored in Blue and Green Represent Oil-Saturated Sand

The obtained result further established the behaviour of the reservoir properties and elastic parameters in thinly bedded reservoirs (Tables 2, 3 and 4) which is the same within thick reservoirs.

Table 2. Elastic Parameters for the Reservoirs in Well 001

Well	Mu(PSI x 10 ⁶)	K(PSI x 10 ⁶)	E(PSI x 10 ⁶)	PR	Lambda(PSI x 10 ⁶)	M(PSI x 10 ⁶)
AJ 2	0.13487	1.202348	0.391442	0.4465	1.112424	1.383645
BJ 2	0.388686	1.719842	1.081531	0.397	1.460515	2.237917

Note: Where M = Primary-Wave Modulus, E = Young's Modulus, Mu = Shear Modulus, K = Bulk Modulus, PR = Poisson Ratio, Lambda = Lamé's Constant, c = Compressibility, S/c = Mu-compressibility Ratio.

Table 3. Elastic Parameters for the Reservoirs in Well 004

Well	Mu(PSI x 10 ⁶)	K(PSI x 10 ⁶)	E(PSI x 10 ⁶)	PR	Lambda(PSI x 10 ⁶)	M(PSI x 10 ⁶)
AJ 2	0.229202	1.361889	0.650682	0.4209	1.209280	1.667774
BJ 2	0.682097	2.092154	1.842544	0.3547	1.637432	3.001686

Note: Where M = Primary-Wave Modulus, E = Young’s Modulus, Mu = Shear Modulus, K = Bulk Modulus, PR = Poisson Ratio, Lambda = Lamé’s Constant, c = Compressibility, S/c = Mu-compressibility Ratio.

Table 4. Elastic Parameters for the Reservoirs in Well 005

Well	Mu(PSI x 10 ⁶)	K(PSI x 10 ⁶)	E(PSI x 10 ⁶)	PR	Lambda(PSI x 10 ⁶)	M(PSI x 10 ⁶)
AJ 2	0.327190	1.553339	0.916928	0.4018	1.335173	1.989758
BJ2	0.430602	1.763209	1.191484	0.389	1.476179	2.337413

Note: Where M = Primary-Wave Modulus, E = Young’s Modulus, Mu = Shear Modulus, K = Bulk Modulus, PR = Poisson Ratio, Lambda = Lamé’s Constant, c = Compressibility, S/c = Mu-compressibility Ratio.

The P-wave modulus M has a range of values within which the sand to be produced has no drilling-related risks most especially sand production. The threshold value for which the Primary-wave Modulus is considered safe enough to ensure a drilling free of sand production is: 1.5×10^6 PSI to 3.0×10^6 PSI (Tixier *et. al.*, 1975). The values of p-wave modulus calculated across the wells in both reservoirs fall within the range stated above. This corresponds to the fact that the reservoirs are located in geologically young formations. The V_p -Porosity cross plot generated also proves this fact. The shear modulus to compressibility ratio is normally needed to ensure also that sand control will be needed values equal to or less than 0.7×10^6 psi². All the values of the Mu/c ratio calculated are less than this threshold value. The values were between $0.13 - 0.68 \times 10^{12}$ psi². Furthermore, the obtained results showed that the velocity of a seismic wave is dependent on porosity, liquid, and/ or gas filling the pore spaces, the degree of saturation for each constituent, and fluid distribution within the rock. Besides, it affirmed that amplitude is dependent on both the velocity disparity on the interfaces and on the interference effects between individual reflections when the reflecting interfaces are close together. It was established that acoustic impedance is related to porosity and/or the presence of hydrocarbon.

Finally, the new model, Power Law equation generated from the cross of velocity ratio against acoustic impedance which is hyperbolic (non-linear), as against the linear equation for thick reservoirs, can be used in obtaining acoustic impedance from the velocity ratio or vice-versa. This might be due to differences in layer thickness. The advantage is that the uncertainty and the effects of the spatial variations in the parameters are propagated accurately and can be quantified as it is within thick reservoirs. The litho-facies have been classified at a sub-seismic resolution which makes it potent, thereby mitigating drilling risk and increasing the confidence in the obtain result.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated detailed integrated approach that enhanced effective quantitative interpretation through which the viability and reservoir quality of the thin-bedded reservoirs in Jude field’, Offshore, Niger delta basin has been assessed irrespective of the thickness. By-passed hydrocarbon reserves were identified efficiently within stratigraphic thin beds for improved production using the static and dynamic properties of the reservoirs. Variations in porosity, compressional velocity, and modulus within thin reservoirs in Agbada formation allowed for better interpretation of the subsurface as prospects (new well locations) were proposed. Relationships between the reservoir and elastic properties determined provided direct attributes for the reservoir model. Reservoirs AJ2 and BJ2 are potential pay zones, favourable because of adequate porosity values, water saturation values are low, high values of hydrocarbon saturation (S_h), good permeability, and exceptional net to gross. The templates as well as the Power Law equation generated from the rock physics will facilitate the knowledge of the elastic properties of thin beds within the Miocene -

Pliocene sandstone in Agbada formation, Niger delta. New drilling locations were proposed with hydrocarbon prospects at the north-eastern part of the existing wells. This integrated approach can be applied to other hydrocarbon basins for further study. Advanced, innovative exploration and extraction technologies such as horizontal and directional drilling, infrasonic compliant distinctive spectroscopy, and more advanced oil recovery methods can be favourably appropriated to harness the hydrocarbon in these by-passed zones and places where drilling was once uneconomic.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors express their thanks to TWAS / CNPq (Brazil) and Needs Assessment (Nigeria) for funding the research. Special thanks to the Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, and Institute of Energy and Environment, University of Sao Paulo, Sao Paulo, Brazil for the opportunity to carry out the project. We equally appreciate Shell Nigeria Exploration and Production Company Limited (SNEPCo) for the data used for the research.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Oluwadare O. A: Conceptualization, Resources, Methodology, Writing – original draft

Enikanselu P. A: Supervision, Validation, Editing

Taoli F: Supervision, Funding acquisition

Olowokere M. T.: Project Administration, Supervision, Funding acquisition

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